

TABLE CONTINUED

Application rate of soil amendments in 1976 (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)							
	1976-77		1977-78		1978-79		3-year average	
	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat
Pyrite								
0	1.1	0.8	1.6	1.1	2.0	1.1	1.6	1.0
1.5	1.7	1.3	2.8	1.6	3.1	1.7	2.5	1.5
3.0	2.7	1.7	4.0	2.1	4.3	2.3	3.6	2.0
4.5	4.2	2.6	5.2	2.6	5.6	2.8	5.0	2.7
6.0	4.6	3.5	5.9	3.1	6.0	3.5	5.5	3.3
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.4

in each of the 3 years.

IR24 (1976) and Jaya (1977 and 1978) seedlings were transplanted at 5 to 6 weeks at 15-cm spacing with 4 to 5 seedlings/hill. Nitrogen was applied at 120 kg/ha, with 22-26 kg P, 26-33 kg K, and 35-40 kg ZnSO₄/ha.

Wheat varieties HD1982 (1976) and HD1553 (1977 and 1978) were sown at

125 kg/ha in rows spaced 20 cm apart. Fertilization was 100 kg N, 17-28 kg P, 8-26 kg K, and 20 kg ZnSO₄/ha. To avoid termite damage, 16 kg BHC/ha was applied. Crops were irrigated when needed.

Rice husk and sawdust application did not affect rice or wheat yields. Yields in 1976 were 1 t rice/ha in untreated plots, 5.3 t in gypsum-treated plots, and

4.6 t in pyrite-treated plots. Wheat yields increased from 1 t/ha to 4.8 and 3.5 t/ha for gypsum- and pyrite-treated plots (see table).

Data showed a substantial residual effect of gypsum or pyrite treatment, and indicated a rice - wheat - green manure cropping pattern does not cause rapid reversion of reclaimed alkali soils.

Comparison of traditional and alternative cropping systems in Cagayan, Philippines

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Three maize-based cropping systems were compared for profitability with the farmer's pattern on the floodplains of Solana, Cagayan, Philippines. Profitability was measured by farm gross margin technique, which is the difference between gross farm income and current total variable costs (TVC) of production. The study was conducted during the 1981-82 dry and wet seasons. Each pattern was tested

in a 1,000-m² plot with 4 replications.

Mungbean yielded best during wet season because of a uniform rainfall pattern. The second mungbean crop suffered from declining rainfall after Dec. However, wet season crops often are flooded in early Aug when they are at critical growth stages.

Test crops planted in late Apr escaped flooding and heavy rainfall during critical growth stages, but not at harvesting stage.

In the traditional pattern yields of crops established later than mid-May are substantially reduced by heavy rain and flooding, especially on lower fields. Research showed that the physical environment of the area dictates early crop establishment and use of early maturing

varieties that resist damaged caused by flooding and drought.

Experimental maize - maize pattern yielded more than the farmer's maize - maize pattern in both seasons and had a higher return above TVC. Patterns with mungbean following or preceding maize, however, were most profitable, regardless of cultural manipulations. Return above TVC for patterns with mungbean ranged from \$582 to \$667.

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Cost-and-return analysis of traditional and alternative maize-based cropping systems in the river floodplains of Solana, Cagayan, Philippines, 1980-81 cropping season.

Cropping pattern		Yield (t/ha)		Gross return ^a (\$)	Total variable cost (\$)	Profit (GR - TVC) (\$)
First crop	Second crop	First crop	Second crop			
Maize	Maize ^b	2.0	0.8	408	163	245
Maize	Maize	2.1	1.4	591	194	397
Maize	Mungbean	2.6	1.0	928	346	582
Maize	Maize	1.2	2.4	1008	352	656

^a Based on current price right after harvest in the research barangay. ^b Farmer's pattern.